

Appendix 1: Complete list of recommendations for the Caribbean and a summary Infographic.

Recommendations infographic

Complete list of recommendations for the Caribbean

NON-SEVERE COVID-19

Recommendation 1:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19 and low risk of complications, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests against the use of nirmatrelvir-ritonavir (conditional recommendation based on moderate-certainty evidence about effects)

Justification

The panel considered that, in a low-risk population, the benefits of nirmatrelvir-ritonavir were too small compared to the undesirable consequences of its use (drain on resources,

exacerbation of health inequities). Further, significant barriers to implementing the intervention were identified.

The CARPHA recommendation did not change the direction or strength or the original WHO recommendation.

Recommendation 2:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19 and a high risk of complications (i.e., those with comorbidities or immunosuppression), the CARPHA guideline panel suggests using nirmatrelvir-ritonavir (conditional recommendation based on moderate-certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

The benefit of nirmatrelvir-ritonavir may be even higher for unvaccinated individuals with comorbidities or immunosuppression.

Justification

The panel considered that, in high-risk populations, the benefits of nirmatrelvir-ritonavir were moderate and likely to outweigh the undesirable consequences (resource use and exacerbation of health inequalities). However, significant barriers to implementing the intervention were identified in some countries of the region.

Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation changed from strong in favor to conditional in favor.

Recommendations 3 and 4:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests against using molnupiravir (conditional recommendation based on moderate-to high-certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

These recommendations apply to all patients with non-severe COVID-19, regardless of the risk of complications.

Justification

The panel considered that, even in high-risk populations, the benefits of molnupiravir were too small compared to the undesirable consequences (potential use of resources, increment of health inequities). Also, molnupiravir is largely unavailable in many countries of the region.

Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendations maintained its direction and strength in low-risk population (recommendation 3) but changed from conditional in favor to conditional against in high-risk populations (recommendation 4).

Recommendations 5 and 6:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests against using remdesivir (conditional recommendation based on low- to moderate-certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

These recommendations apply to all patients with non-severe COVID-19, regardless of the risk of complications.

Justification

As with molnupiravir, the panel considered that even in high-risk populations, the benefits of the intervention were too small compared to the undesirable consequences (potential use of resources, increment of health inequities). Also, remdesivir requires parenteral administration; therefore, it consumes more resources than other oral antivirals and is difficult to access in the context of saturated health services.

Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendations maintained its direction and strength in low-risk populations (recommendation 5) but changed from conditional in favor to conditional against in high-risk populations (recommendation 6).

Recommendation 7:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel recommends against using systemic corticosteroids (strong recommendation based on moderate certainty evidence about effects)

Justification

The panel considered that in individuals with mild disease, the potential harms of corticosteroids (increment of mortality and adverse events) clearly outweighed their potential benefits.

Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation changed its strength: from conditional to strong against.

SEVERE AND CRITICAL COVID-19

Recommendation 8:

In individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel recommends using systemic corticosteroids (strong recommendation based on moderate certainty evidence about effects)

Justification

The panel considered that in individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the benefits of corticosteroids (reduction of mortality and risk of mechanical ventilation) clearly outweighed their potential adverse events. Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation did not change its direction or its strength.

Recommendation 9:

In individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests using IL-6 blockers in conjunction with corticosteroids (conditional recommendation based on moderate certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

In addition to corticosteroids and supportive care, the use of IL-6 blockers (tocilizumab and sarilumab) probably reduces mortality in individuals with severe and critical COVID-19. However, there are still considerable challenges in supply, access, and affordability for many countries in the Caribbean. Local decision-makers and clinicians should ensure optimal use of this scarce resource, prioritizing their timely access to individuals with greater needs.

Justification

The panel considered that in individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the benefits of IL-6 blockers probably outweigh their potential adverse events. However, the panel also identified considerable challenges in supply, access, and affordability for many countries in the Caribbean.

Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation changed its strength: from ‘strong in favor’ to ‘conditional in favor’.

Recommendation 10:

In individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests using baricitinib (conditional recommendation based on moderate certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

Baricitinib is a valid option for the treatment of severe and critical patients. However, its availability is very limited in the Caribbean. Therefore, decision-makers and clinicians should balance the small potential benefits of mortality with any constraints in implementing the intervention and its opportunity cost.

Justification

The panel considered that in individuals with severe and critical COVID-19, the benefits of baricitinib probably outweigh their potential adverse events. However, its availability is very limited in the Caribbean and most people cannot access it. Compared to the original WHO

recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation changed its strength: from ‘strong in favor’ to ‘conditional in favour’.

Recommendation 11:

In individuals with severe but not critical COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel suggests using remdesivir (conditional recommendation based on very-low certainty evidence about effects)

Remarks:

Remdesivir may have a small effect in reducing mortality in the group of severe patients who are not yet critical. However, the certainty of the evidence for benefit in this group is very low and there are considerable barriers to its access and affordability. Therefore, decision-makers and clinicians should balance the small potential benefits in preventing mortality with any constraints in implementing the intervention and its opportunity cost.

Justification

The panel considered that in individuals with severe COVID-19, the benefits of remdesivir may outweigh their potential adverse events. However, the certainty of the evidence is very low and there are important barriers to accessing the medication. Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation did not change its direction or its strength.

GENERAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ALL SEVERITIES

Recommendation 12:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel recommends against using hydroxychloroquine (strong recommendation based on moderate certainty evidence about effects)

Justification

The panel considered that the potential harms of hydroxychloroquine (increment of mortality and adverse events) clearly outweighed their potential benefits. Compared to the

original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation did not change its direction or its strength.

Recommendation 13:

In individuals with confirmed or suspected COVID-19, the CARPHA guideline panel recommends against using ivermectin (strong recommendation based on very low-certainty evidence about effects)

Justification

Low risk of bias randomized trials shows no benefit of ivermectin in individuals with COVID-19. On the contrary, ivermectin is associated with an increment of adverse events and costs. Compared to the original WHO recommendation, the CARPHA recommendation changed its strength: from ‘conditional’ to ‘strong against’.

Strong recommendations are exceptional in the context of low and very-low certainty evidence. However, in this case, the panel considered that the benefits of ivermectin were unclear, and there was moderate certainty evidence of harm. Making a strong recommendation in this scenario is consistent with GRADE and WHO/PAHO guidance (uncertain benefit-certain harm paradigmatic situation).